

The Impact of Climate Change on the Archaeological Heritage in Kogi State: The Case of Ogori Community

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PAPER KEYWORDS

Climate change,
Heritage loss, Heritage
preservation,
Stakeholders
engagement, Kogi State.

ABSTRACT

There has been growing concern among archaeologists and heritage scholars about the impact of the growing changes in climatic conditions around the world and the adverse effects on cultural heritage. There are concerns about the increasing global temperatures, ecosystem disturbance, and heatwaves, which are considered some of the impacts of climate change today. The preservation of cultural heritage for posterity is a very essential issue to the international community, as it offers significant benefits to the socio-cultural and economic well-being of diverse societies across the world. Cultural heritage serves as a source of cultural identity, linking the present and future generations to their roots. This is in addition to the fact that all aspects of cultural heritage: sites, artefacts, and traditional practices, including cultural performances at festivals and culturally important ceremonies, usually serve the purpose of inviting visitors to a destination as tourist attractions. This is why the current study is important, as it investigates the impact of climate change on archaeological sites in the Ogori community in Kogi State, Nigeria. The research employs archaeological survey, oral interviews, and a review of relevant literature as means of eliciting data. The results indicate that cultural heritage in the Ogori community faces threats from environmental degradation and anthropogenic factors such as erosion, deforestation, indiscriminate bush burning, improper agricultural practices, and mass wasting. The study recommends excavation of both sites as well as collaborative efforts among relevant stakeholders, including community elders, institutions, heritage management organisations, and policymakers, to preserve the community's cultural heritage for posterity.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20409807>

1.1. Introduction

As the vestiges of past human activity, archaeological heritage plays a significant role in cultural and socio-economic development. It serves as a primary source for the reconstruction of the lifeways of past societies by archaeologists, while simultaneously providing insight into past human behavioural patterns, which is valuable for future planning (PHMC, 2015). Further, as tangible manifestations of human cultural expressions, it strengthens cultural identity and promotes cultural value systems (Nomishan and Gubam, 2021). From a socio-economic perspective, archaeological heritage, when transformed into tourist attractions, can boost local and national economies. For instance, the latest Economic Impact Research (EIR) of the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), developed in collaboration with Oxford Economics,

indicates that archaeological heritage contributed EGP 1.4TN to Egypt's GDP in 2024, accounting for 8.5% of the national economy.

Despite these benefits, the preservation of archaeological heritage is faced with significant challenges, particularly the growing environmental degradation, including those caused by natural factors, such as soil erosion and mass wasting, and those exacerbated by anthropogenic activities such as urbanisation, deforestation, and indiscriminate bush burning. Research has shown that the rate of deterioration of archaeological heritage is usually influenced by two factors: the type of archaeological material and the environmental conditions in which it is buried (Pu and Wang, 2023). For example, organic artefacts such as wood, skin and bone are best preserved in a less acidic environment or locations with low, stable relative humidity and consistent temperatures to prevent corrosion, salt damage, and structural degradation. These conditions, when combined, pose a serious risk to the preservation of archaeological heritage. Ogori community, a town with a rich cultural heritage, provides the opportunity for this assessment because of the impact of environmental degradation, such as erosion and mass wasting, on archaeological heritage.

Ogori is a sub-ethnic group in Ogori/Magongo Local Governmental Area (LGA) of Kogi State, Nigeria. Oral accounts trace the origin of the Ogori people to the Yoruba tribe. The people of Ogori believed that they migrated from Ile-Ife while settling intermittently in places like Ilesha, Owo, and Benin before their present location (Akerejola and Gab, 1970). Initial archaeological research in the Ogori community was done by researchers such as Akinade (2003) and Assa (2002, 2010).

Sites in Ogori where archaeological investigations have been conducted are Onumogba settlement, Odokpo hill settlement, and Agada hill. However, these previous research works did not take care of an interrogation of the impact of environmental degradation on the archaeological heritage of the Ogori people. Consequently, these heritage resources stand a risk of destruction, particularly due to the previously mentioned climate change factors. Thus, this research becomes very timely and essential as it explores the impact of environmental degradation on the archaeological heritage in the Ogori community. The study is centred on the Odokpo and Onumogba archaeological sites.

Locating the Study

The Ogori community is located between latitudes 7° 16'N and 7° 30'N, and longitude 6° 6'E and 6° 14'E in Ogori/Magongo LGA of Kogi State in Nigeria, with its headquarters in Akpafa, Ogori. The LGA was created from the old Okene LGA in 1996. It is composed of two communities: Ogori and Magongo, which share similar cultural identity, values, and language. The area is bounded by Okene LGA to the north, Ibilo to the West, and Ekepe to the South. The Odokpo hilltop settlement site is located approximately 1km northeast of Akpafa. It covers a size of 1m x 1m square kilometre. On the other hand, the Onumogba settlement site is located 1.82 kilometres southwest of Akpafa within latitude 7° 26" N and 6° 09" E. The extent of the sites is about 1km. It is situated about 1km away from the local government secretariat (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1: Map of Ogori/Magongo Local Government Area indicating study sites

Literature Review

Environmental degradation is the deterioration of the environment and its resources, such as air, water, and the soil. It is a process that occurs either through natural processes, such as erosion or mass wasting, or through anthropogenic factors such as erroneous farming practices, deforestation, and urbanisation, among others. Existing literature on the impact of environmental degradation on archaeological heritage, particularly in Nigeria are very scarce. While research in environmental degradation in Europe and North America is abundant, research in Africa has received little attention, with studies in Africa accounting for only 1% of the global literature on climate change impact on heritage literature (Fatorić and Seekamp, 2017). Nonetheless, over the years, scholars in Africa have recognised the need to examine the implications of climate change, a driver of environmental degradation, on different forms of heritage in the region (Brooks et al., 2020).

This review is divided into two sections. The first provides an overview of archaeological investigations that have been carried out in Kogi State. This is because the communities within the state share similar climatic and environmental characteristics, such as rainfall, as in Ogori. The second explores and analyses existing literature on the impact of environmental degradation on archaeological heritage in Kogi State.

Assessing the Archaeological Investigation in Kogi State

Archaeology in Nigeria is a recent development, with the first excavation carried out by Leo Frabinus in 1910. Consequently, there has been an increase in the number of archaeological research projects in Nigeria (Connah, 2003; Shaw, 1981). A lot of these have focused on the reconstruction of the history of people who lived in this part of Africa before the colonial era. Notable archaeological research in the region includes the Nok excavations, which were carried out by Bernard Fagg in 1945 (Fagg, 1969). According to Nomishan et al. (2023, p.665), some of the archaeological heritage in Nigeria includes sites such as the Nok Valley, Turunku, Kabitu Hills, Katsina-Ala Basin, Ibinda and Tse-Dura Complexes, Wo-Mondo, Da'ama, Birnin-Kudu Rock Painting, Iwo-Eleru Rockshelter, Erijiyan Postsherd pavements, Ancient Ile-Ife, Old-Oyo Kingdom, Olumo Rock, Idanre Hills, Ancient Benin Empire, Igbo-Ukwu, and Akwanshi Stone Figurines.

Okpoko (1998) in his study "Archaeology and the study of early urban centres in Nigeria", made an attempt to validate that early urban centres in Nigeria developed independently of external influence. His study made use of ethnographic, historical, oral history, and archaeological evidence, including pottery fragments, settlement mounds, and stone walls. His study revealed that early urban centres in Nigeria developed due to ecological, centralised or quasi-centralised authority, and inter-regional trade with one another. In his survey of early urban centres in Nigeria, such as the Kanem-Borno Empire, the Benin Kingdom, and the Old Oyo Kingdom, he also explored the archaeology of Ojuwo Ata Ogu mound in Igalaland, in the Middle Belt of Nigeria.

According to oral information, the mound was built by Ata-Ebelejonu, one of the first four Igala royal ancestors, to oversee her subjects. As early as the 13th century, Igalaland was already a stratified urban centre, and this was demonstrated by the

existence of a kingship. His research established the antiquity of the region and provides evidence of the existence of early human habitation in the region as far back as the 13th century. His research, like earlier research, only focused on the reconstruction of the antiquity of the Igala people, without consideration of the state of the archaeological materials studied, particularly in light of environmental degradation.

Tubi (2020) in "Anthropological-Archaeological Study of a Late Stone Age Site in Ogidi-Ijumu, Northeast Yoruba Land" studied the Ebere site, a rock shelter in Ogidi-Ijumu of Kogi State, in order to reconstruct the history of the site's past inhabitants. His research employed the use of archaeological fieldwork and anthropological survey as research methods. His study revealed that the site had been inhabited in the past, and this was corroborated by the discovery of several pieces of evidence of past human activity on the site, including potsherds and lithic stones. He also observed that some of the pottery fragments found on the site were worn out.

He opined that this was either a result of their age or due to weathering resulting from their exposure to sunlight, rainfall, and wind. He also noted that the site's cultural significance was threatened due to the activities of farmers in the area. This study is strong because it highlights how human activities, such as farming, contribute to the destruction of archaeological materials, such as pottery, by increasing their fragmentation. When compared to Okpoko's study, his research not only reconstructs past lifeways but also provides an assessment of the state of the site's artefacts. His research, however, did not offer strategies for preserving the artefacts found.

Idris (2016) in "An Archaeological Investigation of Ataba-Apipa Hill-Top Settlement Site in Okaito, Okehi Local Government Area, Kogi State, Nigeria," reconstructed the history of the Egiri people who had occupied the site in the past. He employed oral interviews, archaeological survey, literature review, and ethnographic survey as his research methods. Indicators of past human activity, including house foundations, graves, granary foundations, potsherds, mounds, and grinding stones, were found on the site. He found that the potsherds found in the site were from the pottery made by the Egiri people. Through an ethnographic survey, his research establishes cultural continuity between the Egiri people and the present Okaito people through the ethnographic survey of the pottery-making techniques. He recommends the dating of some of the site's finds and test pit excavations on the mounds found on the site.

Archaeological research in the Ogori community has also provided insight into the lives and lifeways of the Ogori people. These research projects were carried out on the Onumogba and Odokpo hill settlement sites. Assa (2002), in her preliminary research on the Odopko hill (Okesi hill) using archaeological survey and ethnography as her research methods, her research was aimed to reconstruct the past lifeways of the people who had occupied the site. Her study revealed that the site had been used by the early migrants into the area for defensive purposes. The site contained indicators of early human activity, such as grinding stones, defensive stone walls, and potsherds.

Impact of the Environment on the Degradation of Archaeological Heritage

There is an intrinsic relationship between the environment and archaeological heritage. As noted by Pu and Wang (2023), archaeological materials, such as artefacts, after being discarded, go through processes that speed up their deterioration and then, after some

time, stabilise them. However, a change in environmental conditions, no matter how negligible, would disrupt this balance, leading to the deterioration of the artefact. Several studies have studied the relationship between environmental conditions and archaeological heritage.

Brooks et al. (2020), in "African Heritage in a Changing Climate," explored the impact of climate change on different forms of heritage, including archaeological heritage in Africa with a focus on West Africa, North Africa, and East Africa. They employed a multi-disciplinary review of existing literature for their study. Archaeological heritage studied includes rock art, earthen buildings, and sacred groves. They found that heritage in Africa, particularly that of archaeological relevance, was threatened by environmental and climatic changes. For example, sites located along coastal lines, such as the stone town in Zanzibar, have been gradually destroyed due to an increase in sea levels.

They also found that while some sites in the region, particularly in West Africa, had received attention from global heritage institutions, such as UNESCO, less-recognised sites faced destruction from extreme weather events (for example, storm surges and flash flooding), thus stressing the importance of the role of heritage management institutions in the protection of cultural heritage sites. While the archaeological sites in Ogori are not located along coastlines, this research is relevant because it shows how legal protection may help in reducing the impact of environmental degradation on archaeological heritage.

Knight and Grab (2024), in "Vulnerability of Geoheritage Sites in South Africa to Climate Change: Examples from the Eastern Cape Province," studied the impact of climate change on heritage sites in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. By drawing on previous studies and analysing the country's heritage site list database, they examined selected sites of cultural and geological significance in the region. Their analysis revealed that heritage sites in South Africa faced threats from climate change stressors, such as an increase in temperature. For example, the Klasies River cave, a Middle Stone Age archaeological site, was found to be vulnerable to destruction from rising sea levels and increased weathering resulting from temperature and humidity increases.

Similar to the observations made by Brooke et al. (2020), they noted that sites located along the coast were in danger of destruction from flooding. They also noted that increased rainfall could lead to surface instability and potentially destroy building structures. This study is relevant to Ogori because it considers how rainfall could displace artefacts and destroy structures. They also emphasise the role of heritage stakeholders and heritage institutions in the preservation of sites. This will be helpful when providing strategies for the preservation of archaeological heritage in the Ogori community.

Chikodzi et al. (2022), in "Climate Change Risk Assessment of Heritage Tourism Sites Within South African National Parks" studied the impact of changing environments on heritage in South African national parks. Three sites were studied, namely, Mapungubwe, Table Mountain, and Kruger National Parks. They adopted in-depth interviews and focus group discussions as their research methods. Their study revealed that cultural heritage in these sites is highly vulnerable to climate change stressors, including warming temperatures, drought, flood, and rainfall. In the Mapungubwe

National Park, for example, it was revealed that the exposure of artefacts such as pottery to intense temperatures caused breakage due to continuous expansion and contraction.

Furthermore, they noted that artefacts and features on the site yet to be discovered could potentially be washed away by soil runoff from heavy rainfall. Aside from the impact of climate stressors, they noted human activities, such as agriculture near sites, contributed to the destruction of archaeological sites. This research, when compared with places like Ogori, shows how increased rainfall could lead to the displacement of artefacts.

Also, Assa (2010), in "An Archaeological Reconnaissance of Onumogba Settlement Site, Ogori, Kogi State, Nigeria" employed archaeological survey and oral interview to reconstruct the history of the past inhabitants of the site. She found grinding stones, tuyeres, and several potsherds indicating the habitation of the site in the past. In her comparison of the Onumogba and Odokpo settlement sites, she observed how farming activities had destroyed some of the archaeological heritage in Onumogba. She provides two explanations for the lack of features, suggesting settlement on the site. The past inhabitants of the site might have used organic materials such as grass and thatch for the construction of their homes. Alternatively, the stone arrangements which might have been used for the house foundations might have been converted to boundary markers by the farmers. This is similar to what Tubi (2020) observed in his research.

While not archaeological research, Olagboye's (2002) study provides background on the environmental characteristics of the Ogori community. Although not an archaeological investigation, his study is relevant to this research because it provides an overview of Ogori's environmental characteristics. He notes that due to their exposure, rocks found on the hills in Ogori are prone to weathering. Soils on the plains: regular bush burning on the site is also causing erosion. Additionally, soils on the plains, due to their fertility, encourage agricultural activities, which, when left unchecked, could contribute to the destruction of archaeological sites.

This view is supported by Assa's observation at the Onumogba site, where farming activities have disrupted the archaeological context of the site by the use of rocks for house foundations and for delineating boundaries. He notes that the slopes of the hills of Ogori have led to erosion, and this has been exacerbated by the regular bush-burning activities in the area. His study is relevant as it will help in evaluating how the geographical features of Ogori could contribute to the destruction of its archaeological heritage.

Therefore, the existing literature on the impact of climate change on archaeological sites has gradually increased (Bertolin et al., 2015; Borg et al., 2014; Elliott and Williams, 2021; Ezcurra and Rivera-Collazo, 2018; Grøntoft and Cassar, 2020). Review of the literature reveals the increasing threats to archaeological heritage posed by climate change impacts. However, most of these researchers are dominated by studies from other regions of the world, while research in Africa is comparatively little. This research, therefore, aims to contribute to the growing discourse on climate change impacts on archaeological heritage using archaeological sites in the Ogori community as case studies.

While the archaeology of the Ogori community has been studied and documented, there is a gap in these studies on the preservation of their archaeological heritage. As a result, the archaeological heritage of Ogori faces a significant threat of degradation due to environmental factors. It is therefore crucial to investigate the impact of environmental degradation on the archaeological heritage of the Ogori community, being cognisant that archaeological resources are finite. It is therefore on this basis that this research has been conducted.

This research is aimed at assessing the impact of environmental degradation on the archaeological heritage of the Ogori community. The specific objectives are to collect archaeological data from the Onumogba and Odokpo abandoned settlement sites, examine the environmental conditions surrounding the archaeological records from the Onumogba and Odokpo abandoned settlement sites, and assess strategies for mitigating environmental degradation for enhanced conservation and sustainable management of the archaeological heritage in the Ogori community.

1.2. Research Methods

An oral interview is a method in archaeological investigation that involves the researcher having conversations with people in the society. Interviews may be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured. During oral interviews, oral traditions are the primary data for the collection of cultural information about a people. Oral tradition is a form of communication in which collections of cultural information, such as knowledge, values, and symbols, are transmitted from one generation to the next orally (Nogueira, 2003). Forms of oral tradition include legends, myths, stories, and folktales. Oral tradition has remained a reliable source for data collection in archaeological research. For example, it has made it possible to reconstruct the past lifeways of prehistoric African societies that had no written record of their history (Schmidt, 2013). Despite its relevance in archaeological research, archaeologists are careful when exploiting the data provided by oral tradition, as its potency and accuracy are dependent on the memories of successive generations (Rubin, 2009).

The interview with the informant was semi-structured. Questions were prepared before the interview, and more questions were asked during the interview. Oral tradition of the Ogori people for this research was obtained from 12 persons, all of whom were 50 years old and above. The reason for this was that they had more knowledge of the history of the Ogori people compared to those below the age range. Each informant was interviewed individually. The instruments used in the interview were writing materials and a recorder. Archaeological reconnaissance is the preliminary survey of an area in order to identify and record archaeological remains without the disturbance of the subsurface (LibreTexts, 2021). It is usually the first step taken in archaeological research, as it informs archaeologists if additional research is needed. In archaeological reconnaissance, archaeologists employ a variety of methods. These include: aerial reconnaissance, surface reconnaissance and geophysical reconnaissance (LibreTexts, 2021). The methods employed will depend on the research questions, available funding, timeframe of research, and scale of research.

Archaeological reconnaissance on the Onumogba and Odokpo hill settlement sites was carried out using the ground reconnaissance technique, which involved walking over

the site to determine the extent of the site and identify the spatial relationship between finds and features. The instruments used include a camera for taking photographs of material evidence found on the site, a ranging pole for providing a sense of scale, a measuring tape for measuring the height, width and breadth of cultural objects, a digital compass for obtaining the bearing and direction, and a Global Positioning System device for obtaining the latitudes and longitudes, as well as their elevation. The researcher was accompanied by Ezekiel Alabi, who served as his guide and provided assistance during the archaeological reconnaissance. At the end of the reconnaissance, the researcher identified several pieces of evidence of past human activity on the site. Written documents are documented records of past societies. They include manuscripts, scrolls, tax records, maps, and colonial records. In archaeological investigations, written documents complement the material evidence found.

This research elicited relevant information from written documents. They include books on the history of the Ogori people, such as Osheidu's (1980) "The History of Ogor". Additionally, research papers written on the impact of environmental degradation on archaeological heritage in different regions of the world were also studied. These papers were sourced from the Google Scholar database. The database was queried using keywords related to this study, such as "Climate Change and Archaeological Heritage" and "Environmental Degradation and Archaeological Heritage". Published archaeological research in Kogi State was also reviewed. These provided the researcher with the necessary data for the literature review.

1.3. Results and Discussion

As earlier stated, the Odokpo settlement is located on a hill, which can be accessed by a footpath. At the foot of the hill leading to the hill is the old building of the Anglican Nursery and Primary School, Ogori. The terrain of the site is undulating, elevating gradually from the east to the west. Despite its undulating terrain, some areas of the hill are relatively flat. The vegetation of the area is very dense and is composed of both large trees and shrubs. The prominent trees found on the hill include mango, cashew, baobab, and palm trees. It is bounded on the north by the Agada Hill, which runs from the west to the east. The soil type of the site is composed of a mixture of sandy and loamy soil types.

The Onumogba settlement site is a flatland, and its vegetation is characterised by several trees, including mango trees, cashew trees, and locust bean trees. Its soil type is made of alluvial deposits. The vegetation of the area is composed of mango and baobab trees. The site shows evidence of human disturbance, as several parts of the site are used for cultivation, although some parts of the site remain undisturbed with thick vegetation.

The objective of the archaeological reconnaissance and survey at the Odokpo Hill and Onumogba sites was to assess the impact of environmental degradation, including that caused by natural and anthropogenic factors. This involved identifying finds and features on the sites, their distribution, and their surrounding environmental conditions. This would provide the basis for their analysis in the preceding chapter.

Finds and Features

The finds and features were documented. Both sites revealed different evidence of past human activities. The archaeological features that dominated the Odokpo Hill settlement were stone walls. In contrast, the majority of the features on the Onumogba settlement site were mounds of iron slag.

Odokpo Hill

Potsherds

Potsherds were found scattered over the site. They varied in size and in fragmentation (See Plate 7). Most of the potsherds found on the site were concentrated close to stone walls and along the slopes of the hill. A total of 50 potsherds were collected from the site.

Plate 1: Potsherds collected from Odokpo Hill

Grinding Stone A: This is a lower grinding stone that is located within latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 44''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 39''$ E with an elevation of 472.85 above sea level. It is 0.5m long, 0.3m wide, and has a depression of 0.2m. It is located about 1.3m southeast of the second stone wall. It was partly buried and barely visible (see Plate 8).

Plate 2: Grinding Stone A

Grinding Stone B: The second grinding stone found during the survey is a lower grinding stone (see Plate 9). It is found in the western part of the site and lies within latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 42''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 38''$ E with an elevation of 475.41m above sea level. Its length is 0.12m and measures 0.9m in width with a depth of 0.11m. It is located 3m north of the first grinding stone. It is also fragmented, probably due to the action of the physical weathering process caused by water.

Plate 3: Grinding Stone B

Grinding Stone C: The third grinding stone is a lower grinding stone, and it is located in the southern part of the site (see Plate 10). Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 43''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 38''$ E. Its length, width, and depth are 0.5m, 0.3m, and 0.07m, respectively. It is fragmented, indicating that it had undergone weathering processes.

Plate 4: Grinding Stone C

Grinding Stone D: It is located in the southern part of the site and is a lower grinding stone. Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 44''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 39''$ E. It is 0.67m long, 0.32m wide and 0.18m deep. Its elevation is 470.58m above sea level. It has no visible sign of fragmentation. Instead, it shows wear, especially at its edges (see Plate 11).

Plate 5: Grinding Stone D

Grinding Stone E: This is a lower grinding stone located at the northern part of the site with coordinates latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 43''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 39''$ E. It has a length of 0.4m, a width of 0.2m, and a depth of 0.15m (see Plate 12). Its elevation is 471.8m above sea level. It is highly fragmented, with only half of it preserved. This is most likely caused by physical weathering.

Plate 6: Grinding Stone E

Grinding Stone F: This is located at the north-eastern part of the site. It is a local grinding stone. Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 46''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 43''$ E. It has a length of 0.42m, a width of 0.4m, and a depth of 0.2m (see Plate 13). The research observed that the grinding stone was buried by soil. This might be due to erosion, caused by the movement of water that transported earth from the top of the hill downwards.

Plate 7: Grinding Stone F

Feature A (Stone Wall): This stone wall was found in the southern part of the site. It measured 3.8m in length and 0.9m in height (see Plate 14). Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 42''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 38''$ E. It is 472.68m above sea level. The stones that compose the wall are arranged in an irregular pattern. They are made up of quartz. The wall had been covered by the accumulation of earth, possibly due to the action of water that had moved sediment from the top of the hill downwards.

Plate 8: Stone Wall

Feature B (Stone Wall): This wall is 4.4m long in the west and south directions. It is 0.6m high (see Plate 15). Its elevation above sea level is 474.54m. It lies between latitude 7° 27'44" N and longitude 6° 10' 39" E. Like the first wall, this wall had also been buried. Vegetation around it also made it partially visible. The accumulation of earth made it difficult to determine the full extent of the wall.

Plate 9: Stone Wall B

Feature C (Stone Wall): Has a length of 0.3m in the west-east direction and a height of 0.7m. It sits at an elevation of 473.3m above sea level. Its geographical coordinates are latitude 7° 27' 44" N and longitude 6° 10' 39" E. The rock type is sandstone. This wall had not only been overlain with sediment, but was also greatly affected by vegetation growth. A tree obstructed the rock arrangements of the wall (see Plate 16). The arrangement was not complete, as some rocks had probably been moved by the movement of water due to rainfall.

Plate 10: Stone Wall C

Feature D (Stone wall): This wall measures 0.5m in height and has a length of 0.9m in the west-east direction. Its GPS coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 48''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 39''$ E with an elevation of 483.88 above sea level. Compared to the previous walls, the arrangement of this wall was fairly intact (see Plate 17). A tree had grown above the arrangement. The rocks exhibited a greenish colouration with irregular patches of white. This observed colouration might be due to chemical weathering.

Plate 11: Stone Wall D

Feature E (Stone wall): This wall is located at the northern part of the top of the hill. It measures 1.3m in height and 7.7m in length in the west-east direction. Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 47''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 44''$ E with an elevation of 507.2m above sea level. This wall, like the others, was enveloped by the accumulation of soil (see Plate 18). The researcher also noticed that some rocks lay a few feet from the stone wall along the slope.

Plate 12: Stone Wall E

Feature F (Stone Wall): This wall is found in the northern part of the site. It measures 4.8m in length in the west-east direction and has a height of 1.5m. Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 27' 46''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 44''$ E. This stone wall had the highest concentration of granite rocks with varying sizes (see Plate 19). They also exhibited a green colour with patches of white spots, which indicate erosion due to their exposure to water and temperature changes.

Plate 13: Stone Wall F

Figure 2: Site map of the Odokpo Hill settlement site

Onumogba site

Potsherds

Potsherds were on the site, although they were very small in size, exhibiting a high degree of fragmentation. Potsherds found were also few compared to those found on Odokpo Hill (see Plate 20). A total of 14 potsherds were selected from the site.

Plate 14: Potsherds from Onumogba

Tuyere Fragments

6 tuyere fragments were found on the site. They had an average diameter ranging from 0.3m to 0.6m (see Plate 21). Visual observation showed that they were made of mica and quartz. Their width ranged from 9cm to 16cm. They found what appeared to be a collapsed iron smelting furnace, and the openings still had remains of hardened slag. The base of the tuyere was fragmented.

Plate 15: Samples of Tuyere Fragments from Onumogba

Grinding Stone 1: This is a lower grinding stone found in the northern part of the site. Its geographical coordinates are latitude 7° 26' 43" N and longitude 6° 10' 04" E. Its

length is 0.47m with a width of 0.37m, and a depression of 0.16m. It is fragmented, with almost half of the stone left (see Plate 22). Considering its location in a farm, its fragmentation might likely have resulted from farming activities, especially from ploughing with hoes. It might also have been fragmented due to weathering processes.

Plate 16: Grinding Stone 1

Grinding Stone B: This is a lower grinding stone located in the southern part of the site. Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 26' 40''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 09' 58''$ E. It is located very close to the only Baobab tree in the area. It is 0.57m long, 0.53m wide, and has a depression of 0.12m. The degree of fragmentation of this stone is less obvious compared to the other grinding stones (see Plate 23).

Plate 17: Grinding Stone 2

Grinding Stone 3: This is a lower grinding stone located in the northern part of the site with coordinates latitude $7^{\circ} 26' 44''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 10' 06''$ E. It is 0.71m long, 0.27m

wide, with a depression of 0.08m. Some parts of the grinding stone, particularly its edges, showed wear, possibly due to weathering or repeated use (see Plate 24).

Plate 18: Grinding Stone 3

Feature A (Mound of Iron Slag): It is located in the southern part of the site with coordinates latitude $7^{\circ} 26' 36''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 09' 56''$ E. It is 0.88m high and 1.12 m wide north to east. This iron slag mound, along with the others found on the site, was overgrown with vegetation, such as grasses and shrubs (see Plate 25).

Plate 19: Mound of Iron Slag

Feature B (Mound of Iron Slag): This is found in the southern part of the site. Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 26' 36''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 09' 56''$ E. It is 0.73 high and 1.27 wide north to east. A shrub had grown very close to it.

Plate 20: Mound of Iron Slag

Feature C (Mound of Iron Slag): Its geographical coordinates are latitude $7^{\circ} 26' 35''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 09' 56''$ E. It is 1m high and measures 1.40m north to south. It is located in the southern part of the site. This mound was located under a tree with leaves scattered over the surface. A large block of sandstone was found on this mound (see Plate 27).

Plate 21: Mound of Iron Slag

Feature D (Mound of Iron Slag): Located in the northern part of the site, it lies between $7^{\circ} 26' 35''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 09' 56''$ E and has a height of 0.26m and a width of 0.89 north to south. This mound was more concealed by shrubs and climbers compared to the other iron slag mounds (see Plate 28).

Plate 22: Mound of Iron Slag

Feature E (Mound of Iron Slag): This is the smallest iron slag mound. Its coordinates are $7^{\circ} 26' 35''$ N and longitude $6^{\circ} 09' 56''$ E with a height of 0.12m and a width of 0.83 in north to south. Its small size may have been a result of intentional removal by farmers (see Plate 29).

Plate 23: Mound of Iron Slag

Figure 3: Site map of Onumogba settlement site

1.4. Discussion of Findings

Findings from this study reveal that both natural and human environmental degradation are a big threat to the archaeological heritage of Ogori (with an emphasis on the Onumogba and Odokpo hill sites). The findings support the existing body of knowledge, highlighting the susceptibility of archaeological materials to environmental degradation and providing a new focus area within Nigeria, which, to date, has received much less investigation. This study used archaeological reconnaissance, oral interviews, and the physical assessment of the environment to show that archaeological materials (including potsherds, grinding stones, stone walls, and iron slag mounds) are not just indicative of human occupation in the area but are also very vulnerable to degradation when subjected to changing environmental conditions.

A key finding from this research is how different distributions of types of archaeological material are seen between sites. The physical differences in these materials reflect the unique functions and historical uses of the two sites (i.e., Onumogba and Odokpo Hill). The Onumogba site clearly shows evidence of domestic and industrial activities, particularly iron smelting (e.g., tuyere fragments, slag mounds). This is contrasted at Odokpo Hill, where defensive features (e.g., stone walls) support the presence of domestic materials (e.g., grinding stones, pottery). Both of these physical differences

provide supportive evidence for previously established interpretations regarding settlement patterns in the study area, and thus contribute to the understanding of how archaeology facilitates our knowledge regarding the construction of architecture and social/cultural organisation. These functional differences, however, also impact the nature of each site's respective degrees of environmental impact on the surrounding area.

Both sites' potsherds recognised degradation trends, suggesting limited human interference at Odokpo Hill, where potsherds were larger with minimal fragmentation but were more exposed to natural deterioration from rainfall, wind and erosion, whereas the fragmentation and size of potsherds at Onumogba suggested anthropogenic disruptions due to agricultural activities, thus confirming previous research noting hoe use in agriculture as a large contributor to the physical destruction of archaeological materials. Both sites are degraded due to natural processes; they're degraded faster by human activities at Onumogba.

The state of the grinding stones at both sites provides further insight into environmental impacts. At Odokpo Hill, many grindstones were partially buried, severely fragmented as a result of erosion and weathering and have been exposed to the elements, particularly rainfall and temperature changes that lead to physical disintegration. While at Onumogba, the grindstones were associated with both weathering and mechanical damage, and again, farming activities had similar effects on grinding stones, suggesting that both weathering and human activity were degrading the two different types of durable stone artefacts.

The stone walls at Odokpo Hill represent one of the most significant archaeological features in the study, yet they are also among the most threatened. The walls have been largely buried under sediment deposits caused by erosion, and in some cases, disrupted by vegetation growth and root action. The discolouration observed on the stones suggests chemical weathering resulting from prolonged exposure to moisture and temperature changes. This confirms the role of environmental processes in altering not only the structural integrity but also the physical composition of archaeological features. The partial visibility of these walls further complicates archaeological interpretation and underscores the urgency of preservation efforts.

Environmental factors such as topography, soil composition, and climate play a central role in shaping the degradation processes observed at both sites. The steep, undulating terrain of Odokpo Hill, combined with sandy-loamy soil and high rainfall, creates ideal conditions for erosion and sediment displacement. This leads to the burial and movement of artefacts, thereby disrupting their original context. In contrast, the flat topography and loamy soil of Onumogba reduce the risk of erosion but make the land highly suitable for agriculture, which in turn increases human interference. This contrast demonstrates that different environmental settings produce distinct but equally damaging effects on archaeological heritage.

Anthropogenic factors emerge as a dominant force in the degradation of the sites, particularly at Onumogba. Farming activities, bush burning, deforestation, and the repurposing of stones for agricultural use significantly alter the archaeological landscape. The clearing of vegetation exposes the soil to erosion, while bush burning destroys protective ground cover and accelerates soil degradation. Additionally, the removal and

reuse of stones for boundary demarcation or farming purposes directly result in the loss of archaeological context. These activities reflect a lack of awareness about the cultural value of the sites and highlight the need for community engagement in heritage preservation.

Another important finding is the role of vegetation in both preserving and damaging archaeological materials. While vegetation can stabilise soil and reduce erosion, it can also obscure artefacts and cause physical damage through root growth. At Odokpo Hill, dense vegetation has concealed many features, making them difficult to identify and study. At the same time, tree roots have disrupted stone wall structures, leading to their gradual collapse. This dual role of vegetation underscores the complexity of environmental interactions with archaeological heritage and the need for balanced management strategies.

The study also reinforces the importance of integrating oral tradition with archaeological data in understanding site history and significance. Oral accounts provided valuable context for interpreting the functions of the sites, particularly the defensive role of Odokpo hill and the industrial activities at Onumogba. This integration of indigenous knowledge systems with scientific methods enriches archaeological interpretation and aligns with broader calls for inclusive heritage management. However, the study reveals that despite this cultural significance, local practices have not adequately protected the sites, indicating a disconnect between cultural knowledge and conservation behaviour.

1.5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has demonstrated that the archaeological heritage of the Onumogba and Odokpo hill settlement sites in the Ogori community is under significant threat from both natural and anthropogenic forces. Environmental degradation, particularly erosion, weathering, and vegetation growth, has altered the physical integrity, visibility, and spatial context of archaeological materials such as potsherds, grinding stones, stone walls, and iron slag mounds. These processes, intensified by the area's topography, rainfall patterns, and soil composition, have accelerated the deterioration of cultural remains, thereby endangering the preservation of invaluable historical data about the lifeways of the Ogori people.

Furthermore, the study revealed that human activities, especially farming, deforestation, and bush burning, pose even more immediate and destructive threats to the archaeological record. At Onumogba, intensive agricultural practices have led to the fragmentation and displacement of artefacts, while at Odokpo Hill, land clearing and stone removal have disrupted structural features such as defensive walls. These findings highlight the complex interaction between environmental and human factors in shaping site degradation, emphasising that heritage loss in Ogori is not merely a natural process but one deeply intertwined with socio-economic practices.

Importantly, the research underscores the cultural and historical significance of these sites as repositories of Ogori identity, technological heritage (e.g., iron smelting), and settlement history. The material evidence recovered illustrates patterns of domestic life, industrial activity, and defensive strategies, reinforcing the role of archaeology in reconstructing the past. However, the continued neglect of preservation concerns

threatens to erase this knowledge permanently, especially given the finite and non-renewable nature of archaeological resources.

The study further affirms the urgent need for a holistic and sustainable approach to heritage preservation in Ogori. Addressing environmental degradation requires not only technical conservation measures but also the integration of community knowledge, policy frameworks, and adaptive strategies. Without deliberate intervention, the archaeological heritage of Ogori risks irreversible loss, thereby undermining both cultural continuity and future research opportunities.

The study recommends the following:

1. **Need for Systematic Excavation:** There is a critical need for controlled archaeological excavations at both the Onumogba and Odokpo Hill sites. Excavation will enable the recovery of subsurface materials that are currently at risk of being lost to erosion and farming activities. It will also provide more precise chronological data, enhance understanding of site formation processes, and allow for proper documentation and conservation of fragile artefacts. Test-pit excavations should be prioritised in areas with high artefact concentration, such as iron slag mounds and stone wall zones.
2. **Stakeholder Collaboration:** Effective preservation requires strong collaboration among key stakeholders, including local communities, traditional rulers, government agencies, academic institutions, and heritage organisations. Community members, as primary custodians, should be actively involved in site monitoring and protection. Government bodies and institutions should provide legal backing, funding, and technical expertise, while researchers contribute documentation and conservation strategies. Public awareness campaigns and community engagement programmes should be implemented to foster a sense of ownership and responsibility toward heritage resources.
3. **Heritage Management Strategies:** A comprehensive heritage management framework should be developed for the Ogori sites. This should include site mapping, regular monitoring, controlled access, and the establishment of protective measures such as fencing or buffer zones. Conservation techniques, both indigenous (e.g., taboos, cultural regulations) and modern (e.g., artefact stabilisation, vegetation control), should be integrated. Additionally, the inclusion of these sites in cultural tourism initiatives, such as local festivals, can enhance their value while generating economic incentives for their preservation.
4. **Climate Adaptation Measures:** Given the role of environmental factors in site degradation, climate-sensitive adaptation strategies are essential. Erosion control measures such as terracing, drainage systems, and vegetation management should be implemented, especially on the slopes of Odokpo Hill. Reforestation and controlled bush-burning policies can help stabilise soil and reduce runoff. Furthermore, ongoing environmental monitoring should be established to track changes in climate patterns and their impact on archaeological resources, ensuring proactive rather than reactive preservation efforts.

Together, these recommendations provide a multi-dimensional framework for safeguarding the archaeological heritage of Ogori, ensuring its survival for future generations while contributing to cultural identity, research, and sustainable development.

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